

Study on Yield Characters and Yield of Chinese Rice

(J, MP and Mini) and Breeding Ability of Sinthukha and Mini

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Abstract

The purposes of this study were to investigate the effects of NPKS (15-15-15-7) Armo and urea applications on yield characters and yield of Chinese Rice *Oryzasativa* L. (J₂ = Nake No.1, J₃ = Jia You-1512, J₅ = Jia You ZhongKe No.2, MP 54 Yu-Zhen-Xiang, MP-55-Hua Hang-37 and Mini-Yinzhan). The seeds were provided by Fujian Kingsando Development Co. Ltd at China. The study was conducted, at Dagon University Campus, Yangon Region, from July to November, 2016 in the wet season by using Randomized Complete Block Design with four replications under field condition. The individual plot size was 6.0 meter × 3.0 meter (18.0m²), and the plants were sown by hand in row. Starting from 10 Days After Transplanting the sample plants were collected at 10 day intervals, taking 20 cm from each line between the one border rows. From this study it was observed that the yield was highest in Mini and followed by J₂, MP-55, MP-54, J₅ and J₃. It could be suggested that Mini should be planted at this study area. Two selected rice varieties (Sinthukha and Mini) were used to study the breeding ability for yield and yield characters at Azawa village Thongwa Township in Yangon Region, during June to September in the 2017, wet season, by using (Line ♀ x Testa ♂) Fashion for this study, there were 190 fertilized grains collected from total of 559 grains. And then, we have to be carried out further study to stabilize the quality of gene in F₁ (first generation).

Key words: NPKS Randomized Complete Block Design, Line, Testa

Introduction

Rice is the staple food of over half of the world's population. Rice is the most important single food crop in the world today. Its importance will continue to increase in the decade ahead because population growth in rice-consuming areas. The global production of rice has been estimated to be at the level of 650 million tones and the area under rice cultivation is estimated at 156 million hectares. Asia is the leader in rice production accounting for about 90% of the world's production (FAOSTAT, 2000). Rice is considered to be a semi-aquatic annual grass and is commonly grown in paddies, in wetlands or under shallow water (Website-1). Two *Oryzaspecies* are important cereals for human nutrition.

Oryza sativa (Asain rice) grow worldwide, and *Oryzaglaberrima*(African rice) grown in parts of West Africa, both are cultivated plant species. *Oryza sativa* was first cultivated in South-east Asia, India and China between 8000 and 15000 years ago (OECD 1999; Normile 2004). Rice in China is an important component of rice in the world. China is the world's top producer and consumer of rice. Rice production in China plays an important role for the Chinese people and also affects the world rice market (Min, 1989). Plant breeding is a continuous process, among the various breeding approaches available conventional recombinant breeding (hybridization) followed by selection in segregation generation. A breeding programme, the knowledge of genetic architecture of various characters and choice of suitable parents to be used to crossing programme is most important. The objectives of this study are to evaluate the yield characters and yield of Chinese Rice to NPKS (Armo) and urea

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fertilizers, to evaluate the best yield characters and yield of Chinese Rice for this area and to investigate the potential parents for further use in hybridization programme.

Materials and Methods _A

1. Plant materials and experimental sites

The experiment was conducted at the field of Dagon University Campus, Yangon Region, on July to November, 2016 during wet season. The soil texture was silty clay loam and soil pH was 5.32 - 5.36. The experiment included six varieties given name of J₂, J₃, J₅, MP-54, MP-55 and Mini. The individual plot size was 6.0 m × 3.0 m (18 m²) and fertilizer was applied as NPKS (15-15-15-7) and urea, 2:1 (Kg/ acre) and pest control was done by application of the Chlorpyrifos 40 EC.

Figure A. 1 Fertilities (NPKS and urea) and pest control

2. Sowing practices and managements

Preparing of the nursery starts one month before sowing the nursery. It is important to select the good rice seeds sown in seed beds. The rice is transplanted after sowing one month. The distance between row to row and plant to plant was 20 cm apart.

3. Collection of Data

Starting from the 10th Day After Transplanting (DAT) the plants were collected at 10-days intervals. Take 20cm apart from each line between the one border rows.

Figure A. 2 Preparing the soil, transplanting

Yield Characters and Yield

Data on individual plant was recorded from the twelve plant randomly selected. Total grain yield was estimated from the actual harvest area. number of tiller per m², number of panicle per m², panicle length (cm), number of filled grain per panicle, number of unfilled grain per panicle, filled grain percent, yield (Kg ha⁻¹), yield per acre, were measured and yield was estimated. The number of grain (spikelets) per panicle was determined from five panicles taken at random from harvest rows.

Figure A. 3 Data collection

Materials and Methods _B

Plant materials and experimental sites

Two rice cultivars namely Sinthukha and Mini, using line♀ x Tester♂ mating design at Azawa Village, Tongwa Township, Yangon Region.

Female plant
(Sinthukha)

Male plant
(Mini)

Figure B.1 Two parents

Methods

Crossing procedure

The varieties sown at soil texture were silt loam and soil pH was 4.31. Thirty days old seedlings of each variety were transplanted in 7 feet × 5 feet (35 ft²) with the spacing of 20 × 20 cm.

Emasculation of female plants

Healthy single plants of each variety used as female plants. These female plants were taken from the field before blooming. Panicles were emasculated in the evening about 3-4 PM by using scissors and forceps. About 3 to 5 panicles of each variety were emasculated to produce about 200 crossed seeds of each cross

Pollination

In the following morning, panicles from male parents were collected from the field between 9 to 10 AM. When the panicles were started blooming the paper bag which covered the emasculated female panicles were removed and blooming panicles were gently brushed over the emasculated panicles. The paper bags were covered again onto the pollinated panicle and labeled which mentioned cross combination and date of pollination was tied to the panicles.

Figure A. 4 Growth and Development of Rice (*Oryzasativa* L.)

Table A. 1. Mean plant height of Chinese rice varieties in relation with age

Table A. 2. Mean Number of tillers of Chinese rice varieties in relation with age

Data collection

To use plants in each plot will be randomly taken to collect the data, according to-

1. Plant height (cm) at maturity
2. No. of Tillers per m²
3. No. of panicle per m²
4. Panicle length (cm)
5. No. of filled grain per panicle
6. No. of unfilled grain per panicle
7. Filled grain percent (%)
8. Yield (kg ha⁻¹)
9. Yield (basket per acre)

Figure B. 3 Transplanting and data collection

Results

Growth and Development of Rice (*Oryzasativa* L.)

The rice plant has a fibrous root system bearing erect culms and developing long flat leaves. The culm or stem is made up of nodes and internodes in alternate order. (Chang and bardenas , 1965; Mc Donald, 1979; OECD, 1999). A branch of the plant bearing the root, culms, leaves and often a panicle, is called a tiller. Primary tiller emerges from nodes near the base of the main culm and secondary and tertiary tiller emerge sequentially from these. The node bears a leaf and a bud which may grow into a tiller or shoot. The vegetative organs consist of roots, culms, and leaves. The rice plant is an annual grass with round, hollow, jointed culms rather flat leaves, and a terminal panicle. It is adapted to growing in flooded soils, but it also grows well in non-flooded soils. The panicle is a group of spikelets borne on the uppermost node of the culm. A spikelets is the unit of the panicle, and consists of two sterile lemmas, the rachilla and floret. The flower consists of six stamens and a pistil. The stamens are composed of two-celled anthers borne on slender filaments, while the pistil consists of the ovary, style and stigma. The style is short and bears two plumose stigma. The grain is ripened ovary, with the lemma, palea, rachilla and the awn (Yoshida, 1971; Mc Donald, 1979; OECD, 1999).

Development of crossed seed and harvesting

About 25 days after pollination when the seeds turned to the brownish colour the panicles were cut and the seeds will thresh by hand. The naked seeds were dried and placed in small envelopes. These envelopes will label and number of crossed seeds had mentioned. The F₁ hybrids were generated.

Figure B. 2 Crossing procedure and development of crossed seed and harvesting

Varieties DAS	J ₂	J ₃	J ₅	MP- 54	MP- 55	Mini
40	39.79	38.82	39.54	35	32	41.61
50	50.77	44.28	48.4	45	42	51.54
60	64.16	60.07	59.98	55	50	60.74
70	71.01	74.46	67.9	65	55	74.81
8	88.52	78.63	81.31	76	76	78.49
90	90.16	80.1	83.58	87	93	78.98
100	91.52	80.88	83.88	92	96	85.17
110	93.12	81.81	82.17	89	94	76.17
Mean	73.63	67.38	68.35	68	67	68.44

Varieties DAS	J ₂	J ₃	J ₅	MP- 54	MP- 55	Mini
40	152	93	69	50	50	200
50	188	83	77	100	125	250
60	260	110	98	150	175	275
70	342	131	138	200	225	300
80	302	152	127	250	275	325
90	317	146	133	300	325	350
100	329	167	127	250	350	375
110	365	173	144	300	350	400
Mean	282	132	114	212	234	309

Figure A. 5. Mean plant height of Chinese rice varieties in relation with age

Figure A. 6. Mean Number of tillers of Chinese rice varieties in relation with age

Table.A. 3. Chinese rice of Yield Characters and Yield at Harvest

No.	Treatment	J ₂	J ₃	J ₅	MP-54	MP-55	Mini	CV%	5%LSD	F test	Remark
1.	No of tillers per (m ²)	400	173	152	265	313	435	19.7%	55.47	7.83**	s
2.	No.of panicle per (m ²)	365	167	127	233.33	302.50	397.92	23.1%	61.02	7.81**	s
3.	Panicle length (cm)	19.41	20.12	18.89	19.99	21.69	23.03	10.2 %	1.68	20.08**	s
4.	No of filled grain per panicle	64	47	58	62	63	82	15.5%	8.91	32.94**	s
5.	No of unfilled grain per panicle	21	54	33	31	22	22	36.9%	8.46	7.70**	s
6.	Filled grain percent	73	54	57	70	72	79	10.9%	6.38	24.15**	s
7.	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	3517	1321	2678	2784	3140	3996	27.8%	720.16	8.61**	s
8.	Yield (basket acre ⁻¹)	68	28	38	54	62	78	27.4%	13.83	8.95**	s

s: Significance

Number of tillers per m²

Figure A. 7. Chinese rice of Number of tillers per m² at harvest time

Number of panicle per m²

Figure A. 8. Chinese rice of number of panicle per m² at harvest time

Panicle length

Figure A. 9. Chinese rice of panicle length at harvest time

Number of filled grain per panicle

Figure A.10. Chinese rice of Number of filled grain per panicle at harvest time

Number of unfilled grain per panicle

Figure A. 11. Chinese rice of Number of unfilled grain per panicle at harvest time

Filled grain percent

Figure A. 12. Chinese rice of Filled grain percent at harvest time

Yield (kg ha⁻¹)

Figure A.13. Chinese rice of Yield at harvest time

Yield (basket acre⁻¹)

Figure A. 14. Chinese rice of Yield at harvest time

B. Performance of Two Parents and Hybrids

The mean performance of the two parents for eight characters were namely, plant height, number of tillers per m², number of panicle per m², panicle length, number of filled grain per panicle, number of unfilled grain per panicle, filled grain percent, yield (kg ha⁻¹), yield (basket per acre). Among the two parents, Mini was the lowest in plant height, panicle length, number of filled grain per panicle and filled grain percent However, number of tiller per m² and number of panicle per m² were the highest than other characters.

Figure B. 4. The two parents

In hybrid, by using (Line ♀ x Testa ♂) Fashion (Kempthorne, 1957), there were 190 fertilized grains collected from total of 559 grains. The yield of F₁ hybrid of fertility percent was 34%.

Figure B. 5. Fertilized grain

Table B. 1. Mean plant height of Chinese rice varieties in relation with age

Varieties DAS \ Sinthukha	Sinthukha	Mini
44	45.18	48.99
58	56.28	65.8
72	82	79.86
86	98.99	88.4
100	115.17	93.3
114	103.67	78.36
Mean	83.55	75.79

Table B.2. Mean Number of tillers of Chinese rice varieties in relation with age

Varieties DAS \ Sinthukha	Sinthukha	Mini
44	175	250
58	250	275
72	275	325
86	275	350
100	325	375
114	350	375
Mean	275	325

Figure B. 6. Mean plant height of Chinese rice varieties in relation with age

Figure B.7. Mean Number of tillers of Chinese rice varieties in relation with age

Table B. 3. Sinthukha and Mini Rice of Yield Characters and Yield at Harvest

No.	Varieties Parameters	Sinthukha	Mini
1.	No of tillers per (m ²)	358.33	379.17
2.	No.of panicle per (m ²)	331.25	337.67
3.	Panicle length (cm)	19.43	16.04
4.	No of filled grain per panicle	93.83	48.50
5.	No of unfilled grain per panicle	22.83	41.25
6.	Filled grain percent	82.58	54.08
7.	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	3694.67	2124
8.	Yield (basket acre ⁻¹)	72	41

Figure. B.10. Sinthukha and Mini rice of panicle length at harvest time

Figure. B. 11.Sinthukha and Mini rice of Number of filled grain per panicle at harvest time

Number of unfilled grain per panicle

Figure. B.12. Sinthukha and Mini rice of Number of unfilled grain per panicle at harvest time

Filled grain percent

Figure B.13. Sinthukha and Mini rice of Filled grain percent at harvest time

Yield (kg ha⁻¹)

Figure . B.14. Sinthukha and Mini rice of Yield at harvest time

Yield (basket acre⁻¹)

Figure. B. 15. Sinthukha and Mini rice of Yieldat harvest time

Discussion and Conclusion

In this experiments A, the introduced Chinese rice varieties were cultivated in 2016, during wet season at Dagon University campus. The soil texture was silty clay loam and soil pH was 5.32-5.36. The six varieties of Chinese rices are J₂, J₃, J₅, MP-54, MP-55 and Mini. The vernacular name of J₂ is Nake No.1, J₃ is Jia You 1512, J₅ is Jia You ZhongKe No.2, MP-54 is Yu-Zhen-Xiang, MP-55 is Huahang-37 and Mini-Yinzhan. The present study showed that the plant height parameters increased with the application of NPKS, (Armo) and urea with age. In the early stage when the plant was young. But as the plant becomes older, it showed faster growth. This finding was in accordance with Squire (1990).

In this study the Chinese rice of number of tillers per m² at harvest was statistically significant. The highest mean tiller number was recorded for Mini, J₂, MP-55, MP-54, J₃ and J₅. The number of tiller per meter square of Mini is increased with increased in yield. It is

accordance with Kumura and Takeda, (1962) and Jahiruddin *et al.*, (1994) they reported that tiller number, spikelet number are direct effect on yield.

In this experiment Mini rice was observed that yield (kg ha^{-1}) increased with increases in number of filled grain per panicle and panicle length. This finding was in agreement with Tanaka (1980), Hossaian (1987), Shi *et al.*, (1990), Miller *et al.*, (1991) and Ye *et al.*, (2009) they reported the higher grain yields are associated with higher filled grains per panicle and panicle length.

This experiment was observed that filled grain per panicle, filled grain percent and yield of the Mini rice is higher than other varieties.

In this experiments B, the two rice varieties were cultivated in 2017, during wet season at Azawa Village, Thongwa Township, Yangon Region. The soil texture was silt loam and soil pH was 4.3.

This experiment was observed that the yield (kg ha^{-1}) of Myanmar rice (Sinthukha) was higher than Chinese rice (Mini).

The mean tiller number of Mini is higher than Sinthukha. The number of tiller per m^2 of Mini is higher than Sinthukha. Kawano and Tanaka (1968) reported that the tiller number is positively or negatively correlated with grain yield depending on the rice cultivar and crop environment. Whereas the result of these experiment showed that yield of Sinthukha is higher than Mini. Thus this finding was not agreed with Kumura and Takeda (1962) and Jahiruddin *et al.*, (1994) because they reported that tiller number, spikelet number are direct effect on yield.

In this experiment Sinthukha rice was observed that yield (kg ha^{-1}) increased with increases in number of filled grain per panicle. This finding was in agreement with Tanaka (1980), Hossaian (1987), Shi *et al.*, (1990) and Miller *et al.*, (1991), they reported the higher grain yields were associated with higher filled grains per panicle.

This experiment was observed that filled grain per panicle, filled grain percent and yield of Sinthukha rice is higher than Mini.

The results of the experiment A, the Minirice is the highest of yield characters and yield and then followed by J₂, MP-55, MP-54, J₅ and J₃. Therefore Mini rice will be planted at Dagon University Campus. In the experiment B, the two parents (P), Mini was the lowest in plant height, panicle length, number of filled grain per panicle and filled grain percent However, number of tiller per m^2 and number of panicle per m^2 were the highest significant among other characters in this study. The Sinthukha rice was the highest plant height and other characters of panicle length, number of filled grain per panicle, yield (kg ha^{-1}), yield (basket per acre) exhibited the highly significant. In conclusion, the yield of Sinthukha was more higher than Mini rice. Thus Sinrhukha rice will be more suitable planted than Mini rice at Azawa village. In breeding method of (Line ♀ x Testa ♂) Fashion, Line is Sinthukha (female plant) is crossed with Testa is Mini (Male plant), there were 190 fertilized grains collected from total of 559 grains. Further study has to be carried out is stabilize the quality of gene.

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